

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: NYAGATOMA****FIRST NAME: K. ANTOINE****PROGRAM CODE: DMCR****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: PROF. LAURENT CLEENEWERCK**

The page uses US English (for spelling, punctuation rules and formatting references).
The Rule of Style is: Turabian (in-text/parenthetical).
Used Zotero to insert references.
Used the following software: MS Word 2010 on Windows 7.
Note: This document is in US letter ("8.5"x11" format).

APPROACH OF ACADEMIC WRITING

1) Introduction

To start doctorate program at EUCLID University, the first course I started with was international academic writing to meet international professional and academic writing standards. The program inspires students how to attempt writing easily with clear picture in the mind and steps to follow in a logical manner. This course, illustrates and teaches at length easy writing, how to deal with questions and answers or given task, especially when it comes to a thesis statement and an argument (EUCLID 2015, 2). It also, explains how to start writing an essay, response paper, major papers and what to begin with at any given situation. The aim of this response paper one is to provide feedback on ACA-401D and will discuss briefly on research topic, referencing, quotation, rules of thumb for writing papers, and finally important remedies as well as conclusion.

2) Research topic

The EUCLID manual reminded me that whatever chosen topic should be researched to be able to draw work to other researchers and writers. Despite that, it also emphasizes, reading, making the notes from the readings, organizing the ideas, having first draft as a structure as well as framework that highlights, introduction, body and the conclusion (EUCLID 2015, 3–4). By considering framework, it ignites

the research what to establish with and end up for in order to stipulate international requirements or standards of Academic writing.

3) Referencing

The EUCLID University manuals and references have inspired me on referencing every work especially papers using a fantastic application called zotero as an international electronic tool that facilitates students to provide references within the response papers in a professional manner. First of all, zotero training triggered a positive challenge that enforced me to learn it first and at a later stage apply it so as to attain the period one objective. The coursepack, period one guards against the attempt of plagiarism, which is an academic offence in the field of academics. It further undertakes areas such as, editing the essay, questions to ask yourself before you embark on the essay writing, how to write excellent paper while avoiding plagiarism and with proper citation of references (EUCLID 2015, 5–18). This type of referencing the essay holds the international outstanding values.

4) Quotation

The EUCLID University coursepack, explains quotation as words of authors, which require proper quotation to capture what the author has said or mentioned in the research (EUCLID 2015, 19–22). The course pack also advises the students to observe how to paraphrase, because this is the work of other authors (EUCLID 2015, 23–27). In order to have a sound and presentable essay or research work, there is a need to limit paraphrasing to be able to produce individual original words or statements. Responding to the course manual and template, the expected output will be valued as quality product ready to be consumed by everyone without bias precisely when it comes into the field of study. The course manual enforces writing discipline specifically to personal vs. academic style. It details the avoidable statements; such as “can’t,” “won’t,” and “isn’t” to be applied in a formal of academic style especially with personal examples in order to strike balance between the two styles. It encourages writers who want to achieve logical flow for longer papers to use headings based on provided EUCLID template (EUCLID 2015, 39–42). Applying the citation rules and procedures will help to attain course objectives and learning outcome.

5) Rules of thumb for writing papers

The EUCLID university manual provides ten rules to put into consideration before writing the papers, for example; stating the main thesis of paper, staying focused to be able to assess some important aspect of theories, not to conclude with, or otherwise, writing clearly and not plagiarizing. Plagiarizing appears into two forms, first, using the words without quotation marks and secondly taking ideas from

the source without footnotes. Adopting these rules demand enough time of editing work. However, additional time is paramount. Therefore, papers for this course will be better than they would otherwise be. Technically, editing goes with writing all the time and when practiced, results will meet the required university standards (EUCLID 2015, 43–45). Therefore, it is a student's obligation to grasp it to acquire knowledge and skills at the end of the doctorate program.

6) Important remedies

The EUCLID reference material provides solution for the student to prevent irrelevant grammatical errors such as joining two independent clauses, use of a comma followed by a conjunction, a semicolon alone, or a semicolon followed by a sentence. It also encourages using commas to bracket nonrestrictive phrases, because these are not essential to the sentence's meaning. For this case, EUCLID manual advises students to think in advance the appropriate remedies to mitigate non professional errors. Furthermore, a sentence with an introductory phrase or an introductory dependent clause should include a comma (EUCLID 2015, 46). To comply with all of these remedies, at the end will result in encouraging response papers, major papers as well as theses and dissertations.

7) Conclusion

At the start of writing the first response paper, in the introductory part, it discusses the importance of this course; it's relevance in academic environment, choosing a researchable topic to be able to draw work to other authors or writers, referencing essay, quotations, rules of thumb for writing papers and important remedies to revisit in order to produce a recommendable end results. The EUCLID University ACA-401 coursepack ends with style guide and underlines its importance to every student. The EUCLID University recommends the use of Chicago Rules (Turabian), but other international recognized rules are also fine. Finally, the style should be inline with the known types of writing such as technical writing, commercial or business writing, journalism and web copywriting. Furthermore, it should highlight consistent writing style to allow more than one author to contribute other than carrying personal style of writing but of the different publications. It has been reviewed that many creative writers' need a style guide to ensure that the data delivered is in an acceptable form to maintain previous deliveries or other publications that the customer already has or accessed (EUCLID 2015, 52). This seems difficult and tiresome but it's the most international reliable standards to bear in mind when embarked on the learning journey.

REFERENCES

EUCLID, ACA-401D. 2015. *International Academic Writing (Doctorate)*. EUCLID University.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.